

PRESENT TENSE IN UZBEK, RUSSIAN AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. In this article, the comparison of the verb word category in Uzbek, Russian and Karakalpak languages, the present tense form of the verb, similarities and differences were studied.

Keywords: verb word category, present tense, tense, base, consonant, vowel, affix, present-next tense, definite present tense, present tense continuation verb.

Verb-the richest in grammatical categories in all 3 languages, grammatical nature is the most complex category. Words belonging to the verb word category indicate the process.

The action, state meaning of a verb is expressed through its special grammatical categories. The verb has grammatical categories like rank – zalog – da'reje, mile – naklonenie – meyl, tense – Vremya – Ma'ha'l, person and son – liso I chislo – bet Ha'm san in all 3 languages.

The verb stands out among all word categories in terms of its versatility in meaning, its richness in grammatical categories, forms, as well as its most important place in the composition of the sentence. The Russian linguist academician Peshkovsky was certainly right when he said: "when word categories are compared to planets, the verb is the sun among them." The use of the verb as a central clause in Uzbek also proves this¹.

In Uzbek, the forms of the present tense are several, from which the present-tense form is formed with the verb base ending in a consonant, the-A - affix, if ending in a vowel, the-Y - affix and the tusker displacement². For example: gapir-a-man, gapir-a-san, gapir-a-di, gapir-a-miz, gaoir-a-siz, gapir-a-dilar, axi-y-man, axi-y-san, axi-y-di, axi-y-siz, axi-y-siz.

In Russian, however, the declension of the verbs of the Present Tense will be 2 different. Their difference occurs in which Tuskers are added. For example: in the singular number I, the affix-U(-Yu) in person I: pish-U, rabota-Yu, in person II, the affix -Esh: pish-Esh, rabota-esh, in person III, the affix-ET: pish-ET, rabota-ET; in the plural number, the affix -em in person I: pish-em, rabota-em, in person II, the affix -ETE: pish-ETE, in person III, the affix-ut, -Yut: pish-ut, rabota-Yut. Now let's look at the II tussle. The singular number is affix-U(-Yu) in person I: -molch-U, Govor-Yu, in person II -ish affix: molch-ish, Govor-ish, in person III -it affix: molch-it, Govor-it, and in plural number i person -im affix: molch-im, Govor-im, in person II -ite affix: molch-ite, Govor-ite, in person III -at, -Yat affix: molch-at, Govor-Yat is. In this way, in Russian, the tuslanguage will be 2 different.

In Karakalpak, however, the verb indicates that the present tense of the verb is in the same vatq as the time of speech of the case-action processing. For example: hot messages spilling on Murattin gelip perfume. Present tense forms are expressed through synthetic and analytic verbs. The synthetic type of present tense in Karakalpak is made through the

¹ Muhiddinova X va boshqalar. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. Toshkent. 2006. – B. 110.

² Azizov O. va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent, 1965. – B. 62.

following verb forms: (a) the person-number Affixes are added to the verbs of the case-denoting otir, Ju'r, tur, jatir directly or through the -ip, -ip, -P form of the verb hol, making the present tense. For example: otirman, jatirman, turman, Ju'rmen. (B) the reduced perfume form of the verb jatir is added in the form of bar, kel with verbs, baratir, kiyatir, which takes the suffixes -A,- e of the verb hol, to make the present tense form. For example: Bektemir menen Hojan birge baratir. d) the present tense form of the verb is made through the forms - (i/i)-WDA, -wde, -maqta, -mekte of the action name. These forms of the present tense are tinged with Person-number affixes in person I and person II³. For example: singular number i person: islewdemen, kelmektemen, islewdesen 'in person II, kelmektesen', islewde in person III, kelmekte; plural number I Person: islewdemiz, kelmektemiz,² person islewdesiz, kelmektesiz, 3 person islewdesizler, kelmektesizler.

In Russian, the form of the past tense from some verbs is made differently. 1. Denotes a constant, time-limited action. Such a meaning of the present-next Tense is expressed in Russian by the form of the present tense⁴. Issue: Zemli vratshaetsya vokrug Solntsa. Moi roditeli rabotayut V shkole. Biblioteka ejednevno otkrivaetsya v 9 chasov utra. 2. The next time represents. Such a meaning becomes clear when a word comes to mean the moment. Such a meaning of the present-next Tense is given in Russian by the next tense form of the verb. For example: Zavtra sbortshiki budut rabotat na polyax chetvertoy brigade. Torjestvennoe Sobranie otkroetsya V 7 chasov. Razdali obetshanie, vipolnim.

In Uzbek, the exact present tense form of the verb is made with the addition of the affix -yap or -yotir and the tuslovci. I speak-yap-man. You gapir-yap-san. He is like gapir-yap-ti. In addition, the exact present tense meaning is also expressed by an auxiliary verb. As an auxiliary verb, one of the words stand, walk, sit is used. In this, the leading verb is in the form of the past tense consonant. For example: I read, I speak, I write, like you write. The exact present tense form denotes the action taking place while the speech is being delivered. The exact present tense meaning of the verb is given in Russian mainly by the present tense form of the verb, and in Karakalpak by the exact present tense form. For example: I am doing homework. - Ya vipolniyu domashnie zadanie. - I am a U'yg'e tapsirmalardi islep perfume. I'm writing a letter. - Ya pisho pishma. - I like the letter jazip perfume.

In Uzbek, the present tense continuation verb is formed by adding an affix and a tusker affix in-MOQ. For example: I read, you read, like you read.

The range of use of the current form in Russian is wide. The present tense form of the verb denotes both the action in which the verb is present, and the constant Harkat, and the action limited by the wattage. For example: ya seychas uchus V institute. Volga vradaet V Kaspiyskoe more. Like moi roditeli jivut V Gorode.

In conclusion, we must say that the Present Tense has several meanings and types of meanings in every 3 languages mvjud. Uzbek has verbs of the present tense - present-next tense and the present tense continuation. In Russian, only the verbs of the present tense, that is, the possibilities of the verb of the present tense in this language, are very wide. in Russian, the present tense form denotes both the action in which the verb is present, and the constant Harkat, and the action limited to the vatq. In Karakalpak, however, there are the modern-definite ha'zirgi Ma'ha'l and dawamli kelesi Ma'ha'l forms. Learning languages by analogy will

³ Da'wletov A va boshqalar. Ha'zirgi qaraqalpaq a'debiy tili. - No'kis, 2010. - B. 165.

⁴ Azizov O. va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent, 1965. - B. 63.

be easy and fun for any language learner. It is sure to increase, of course, even the craving for language learning.

References:

1. Azizov O va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti.1965.
2. O.Azizov va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi. Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti. 1986.
3. Bekbergenov A. Rus ha'm qaraqalpaq tillerinin' salistirmali grammatikasi. No'kis: "Bilim" nashriyoti. 2006
4. Da'wletov A va boshqalar Ha'zirgi qaraqalpaq a'debiy tili. No'kis: "Bilim" nashriyoti. 2010.
5. Muhiddinova X va boshqalar. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti. 2006.

